

Facilities & Other Resources

The College of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences at the University of California, Davis has a genomic center with a Q-BOT, a Q-Fill, a HiGro, a Hydro-Shear, high-throughput fingerprinting capacity, and high-throughput sequencing ABI3730 including a robotic station for DNA preparation.

Dr. Dubcovsky's moved in 2011 to a new laboratory (24 benches and 5 service rooms, growth chamber facilities and freezer farm).

Dr. Dubcovsky's laboratory has direct access to the Plant Sciences Dept. UNIX workstation that runs several bioinformatics programs. The lab has 14 relatively new PCs with access to the UNIX station and an Apple workstation with 12 processors and CLC Assembler. We have also access to Cloud Computing capability through Amazon.

J. Dubcovsky's laboratory group has two permanent greenhouses for his program and currently has three additional greenhouses assigned to his group. J. Dubcovsky's has four Conviron Growth chamber and has access to five additional ones at the Controlled Environment Facilities. J. Dubcovsky is the leader of the Wheat Breeding Program at UC Davis and has excellent field and greenhouse facilities for growing large populations of plants. He has access to 20 acres of land in a field located at less than 10 minutes from the laboratory and a Staff Research Associate in charge of the field operations.